

Grant Agreement No.: 680708

Project acronym: HIT2GAP

Project title: Highly Innovative building control Tools Tackling the energy performance gap

Research and Innovation Action

Topic: EeB-07-2015 New tools and methodologies to reduce the gap between predicted and actual energy performances at the level of buildings and blocks of buildings

Starting date of project: 1st of September 2015

Duration: 48 months

D2.1 – Synthesis report on the available and retained solutions for the connection of the HIT2GAP platform to an existing BMS

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Version 1 – Rev.0	Due Date	M14 - 31 th of October 2016
	Submission Date	31 th of March 2017
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Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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Executive Summary

HIT2GAP is inspired from the smartphone Android/ IOS paradigm and aims at developing a kind of an operating system for building energy applications. This OS like environment (called HIT2GAP platform) would then provide some basic functions to allow diverse applications (called HIT2GAP modules) to plug in and make use of them. Similar to Apple's IOS or Google's Android, where third-parties provide various applications on the "Apple Store" and "Google Play", HIT2GAP will also give the opportunity to third-parties to deploy their applications in the HIT2GAP APP Store (Figure 1).

Figure 1. HIT2GAP process description

This paradigm and the subsequent system architecture, that we can refer as system abstraction, will lay on a field level that is in charge of the data collection from the so called "data sources" that must provide the necessary base for the following analysis process in charge of the application layer. The "data sources" can be of various types and can provide data from physical devices as sensors, mobile devices etc. or logical devices as public web services like meteorological reporting, or BMS systems etc.

Thus, HIT2GAP has to deal with the integration of heterogeneous systems and the collection of data from different sources and with different operational perspectives. HIT2GAP provides a solid base of data to be used by the modules delivered by the system and supports/proposes multiple interfaces to connect and collect information from heterogeneous data sources (including BMSs commonly encountered in tertiary buildings). This flexibility is demonstrated and validated in the four Hit2GAP pilot sites through the connection of heterogeneous field devices and specific BMSs.

The scope of this report is twofold:

- Describe the different existing solutions allowing the connection to BMSs and the collection of data gathered through these BMSs. This includes the description of each process, stakeholders' responsibilities or actions (opening of the Data Base for instance) and advantages/drawbacks of each solution.
- Describe the solutions retained for the HIT2GAP project to connect to the BMS of the pilot sites as respect to their BMS configuration and specifications, and expectations from the project itself.

Available options and solutions for the connection to an existing BMS

Data collection from a BMS is complex to deal with. This is due to the fact that each BMS provider protects its software from replacement by other BMS providers. This situation usually brings a very difficult path to find an optimal solution. BMSs can be classified in three levels depending on data accessibility, each of them representing an incremental degree of integration complexity:

- **Easy access:** in this case, an external/remote client can access the same data used by the BMS.
- **Average access:** in this case, there is no direct access to the data used by the BMS but a standard protocol is provided. An external client will have to access data through the BMS, i.e. the BMS will act as a data proxy. For instance, a typical solution incorporates a database in which the BMS stores all the data and the external software links to this database.
- **Difficult access:** this case is encountered when a proprietary protocol is used by the BMS. In this situation either the BMS provider is willing to cooperate and open its proprietary protocol or not. In the former case, it would be possible to program the data transfer to an external software while, in the latter case, the only solution is to try to interface directly with the field equipment.

We investigate the most suitable connection methods that can be found on BMS side highlighting the most important criteria and decision-making elements involved in the selection of the method:

- Reading data via public API'S
- Direct access to operational tables of the BMS
- Access to a buffer table generated by the BMS manager
- Batch export of required data
- Implementation of a specific protocol
- Direct access to BMS counter devices

We demonstrate the usage of two different approaches for data collection:

- **Usage of a middleware platform** that provides a wide set of services like data connector, data persistency, real time data consumption and a wide set of API that guarantee the necessary access points for the application to access and use the collected data. To achieve this approach, we will use the IoT Enterprise Grade platform called PLAT.ONE and develop on its base the necessary data connector to each pilot site. With this approach, we will integrate the BMS systems running on Challenger, Nanogune and Wilanow Pilot sites and some external devices like mobile phones, multi measure wireless sensors and other sensors that can be deployed in different configurations.

- **Direct connection** from a BMS to HIT2GAP data model layer. With this approach, we want to demonstrate that the platform will provide all necessary tools to integrate directly a BMS system or other data sources to the platform avoiding any intermediate level. This approach will be demonstrated on NUIG Pilot site with Cylon Control system.

We define for each pilot site the best possible integration pattern and develop the appropriate connector. Each connector is built with a reusable pattern giving us the ability to customize them for specific purposes.

The development process requires a definition of the “data agreement” with the platform by each pilot site responsible, and then we define the basic requirement that each pilot site must accomplish to provide the necessary information. Since each pilot site has different starting points in terms of data quality and different target points in term of possible gap reduction approach, we will collect most suitable data for each of them.

HIT2GAP platform will be tested with the four pilot sites briefly described here.

Nuig Galway

The demonstration site is the New Engineering Building located at National University of Ireland, Galway, Ireland. The building was opened on the 15th of July 2011. The site is mainly a teaching and research facility with offices, classrooms, laboratories and workshops.

It was constructed and commissioned with emphasis on minimising the impact to the environment. This is reflected in the commissioning of solar collectors, a biomass boiler, heat exchangers and other green technologies to set an example for students, who will eventually go on to propagate a green philosophy as alumni of the University.

The collected data will be stored in a MYSQL database at fifteen minute intervals on the field controllers. HIT2GAP modules have a direct access to the collected data with the aim to demonstrate that the platform can manage data directly and is not strictly dependent on an middleware platform. Modules can access data through a web service provided by Cylon. We stored the data into an AWS RDS database and exposed an web service/API for the data. Later on, Cylon will push data to HIT2GAP platform through the APIs defined by the platform.

Challenger

Bouygues Construction’s head office, was constructed in 1998 and refurbished from 2011 to 2014. There are three main buildings in Challenger that cover a total area of 65000 m²: the central atrium, the North Triangle (NT) and the South Triangle (ST). The site is awarded triple certification (HQE®, LEED® and BREEAM®) confirming the very high level of environmental quality achieved by the entirely renovated building.

Data acquisition includes mainly energy consumption data coming from different energy meters distributed in several electrical cabinets and technical rooms on the site.

The implemented connection method consists of a direct access via SQL query to an intermediate buffer table where data, from a selected number of sensors, are persisted automatically by an internal procedure. This method guarantees an efficient protection of the BMS from external access and in the meantime HIT2GAP can gather data at the most suitable rate.

A set of Build-AX sensor are installed in an area of the South Triangle building without integrating them with the BMS. A REST client connector has been deployed to collected data from these sensors accessing the BuildAx LRS).

Other data available on site, such as indoor air quality (indoor temperature, humidity and CO₂), equipment data and weather data, will be collected in the next few months.

NanoGUNE

The demonstration site is the NanoGUNE building located at San Sebastián, Spain. The building was opened in 2008. NanoGUNE is a research center with the mission of performing world-class nanoscience research for the competitive growth of the Basque Country. The site is mainly a research facility with offices and laboratories with clean rooms.

This pilot site is equipped with a BMS to manage heating, cooling, air conditioning and lighting, the system is closed and cannot be accessed using direct access methods. In the meantime, it is necessary to collect extra environmental information and building usage. Due to this condition, we will manage a mix of connection methods: BMS data will be collected by the system and provided into an FTP server to be managed by PLAT.ONE connector and the environmental data will be collected by MM-WSN sensors that will have a direct access via an MQTT connector provided by PLAT.ONE.

Wilanow town Hall

This Pilot site is located in Warsaw (POLAND), it is a public building owned by the City of Warsaw. It is totally dedicated to offices 12.406 m² (with garage) divided in two buildings, 3 floors, grand floor, underground garage. The building is not permanently occupied.

The building is recently constructed (2014), energy sources include the district heating network and the electricity grid (4 chillers for cooling). The BMS (SATCONTROL) manages lighting (DALI system), air conditioning, ventilation, indoor temperature.

Currently the BMS system implemented in the Wilanów Town Hall (buildings A and B) does not fit into the HIT2GAP concept. An extension/upgrade of the system will take place soon. The main feature that has to be implemented is the data acquisition tool, which is missing and will be added. Renewable energies available at the site consists of heat recovery ventilation.

Currently, the BMS situation of the Warsaw pilot site is not completely defined due to the deployment of a new software in the incoming months. For the meantime, it was decided, with the pilot site responsible and the BMS provider, that the data collection will be executed via a MODBUS over IP protocol that will be deployed in order to interface with the BMS.

1 Introduction

The HIT2GAP project focuses on delivering an open platform solution including analytic tools and modular services for commercial buildings based on the large amount of data that can be collected in the buildings. In this system, the Building Management System (BMS) of the buildings is the central element of the process as most of the data related with energy, comfort and system operation is delivered by the BMS already installed in the tertiary buildings targeted by the HIT2GAP solution. Even if additional data can be collected from other kinds of information sources (as described in D2.2 [1]), the BMS is the main provider of data for a given building and therefore a prerequisite for the HIT2GAP solution. As a consequence, the HIT2GAP solution should include and propose different ways of collecting the data from the BMS commonly encountered in the tertiary buildings.

Regarding to the overall architecture of the HIT2GAP solution, the connection to the BMS is realised through the data connector layer as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2. HIT2GAP Functional Architecture

This deliverable provides the results of the work carried out in task 1.2 ‘Field data infrastructure specifications’ within Work-Package 1 (WP1) and task 2.2 ‘Agile solutions for the connection of the HIT2GAP platform to an existing BMS, integration of complementary instrumentation and other information sources’ within WP2. The report describes the existing BMS connection solutions and the analysis conducted on the conditions of application of these different solutions, and the identification of the options which have been retained for the HIT2GAP implementation on the four pilot sites of the project. The report also includes some elements for the validation of the selected option in the real conditions associated with the French pilot site.

1.1 Purpose

The main scope of this report is to describe for each pilot site the available connection methods that can be used to transfer data from each environment to the platform. The first challenge is to create a picture of the ecosystem we are facing and to define, for each pilot site, the best method to collect data. Another important target is to create a set of standard connectors that any future customer of the platform can use in order to transfer data to HIT2GAP and use the existing modules located in the management level of the platform. In order to create a common connectors' base, a common IoT middleware platform, PLAT.ONE, was selected. It enables the users of HIT2GAP to transfer data from their system to the platform, whether they are using existing or new protocols. It should be emphasised that PLAT.ONE is not the only way to transmit data to HIT2GAP. Indeed, using PLAT.ONE is an option that can be overtaken for specific needs. Another connection option based on web services is also envisioned and will be demonstrated within HIT2GAP. This alternative solution will be implemented by Cylon Control (CYL).

Cylon's commitment to the Hit2Gap project is to build a SaaS product, Aspect Energy, to achieve integration with the following modules, and to demonstrate these modules on the Engineering Building in the National University of Ireland, Galway (NUIG).

The scope of this report is twofold:

- Describe the different existing solutions allowing the connection to BMSs and the collection of data gathered through these BMSs. This includes the description of each process, stakeholders' responsibilities or actions (opening of the Data Base for instance) and advantages/drawbacks of each solution.
- Describe the solutions retained for the HIT2GAP project to connect to the BMS of the pilot sites as respect to their BMS configuration and specificities, and expectations from the project itself.

1.2 Contributions of partners

ABO, as deliverable manager, has structured the work and collected all the information related with the pilot sites in terms of existing measurement infrastructure and protocols used within the installed BMS. ABO has also implemented the first connection with the pilot sites in order to demonstrate and validate the PLAT.ONE solution in real conditions. ABO also developed and deployed some dashboards, published on a public server, to provide an instrument for checking the incoming data quality and the connection availability.

Each pilot site manager (BES, GIR, MOS and CYL) provided information about the actual status of each pilot and agreed on a specific protocol to be used to gather data from their systems. Chapter 3 provides for each pilot site the contribution of the partners and a description on the method used to gather data.

TEK provided inputs to the Data Agreement (included in section 7.1). As T2.2 leader, TEK also contributed by providing general reviews of the overall document.

BES contributed to the first tests implemented on the Challenger site aiming at validating the PLAT.ONE implementation.

1.3 Report structure

This document provides the results of the work carried out by the consortium partners involved in sub-tasks 1.2.1 and 2.2.1 have achieved from M1 to M18.

This report is organized in four sections:

- An introduction describes the context and organization of this work;
- Section 2 provides an identification of the existing solutions for the connection to BMS and an analysis on advantages and drawbacks and requirements of each solution;
- Section 3 provides a brief description of each pilot site and particularly basic information about data collection aspects of the site; it gives a summary of the different technologies adopted to realize the appropriate connectors for each pilot site and/ or source of data. A description of the connection being established between the different data sources that can be referred to as a “data agreement” including module structure and parameters is provided;
- Section 4 concludes this report.
- Appendix 1 collects significant details on data sources that do not belongs to a specific pilot site and can be used in multiple situations adopting the same communication schema.

2 Available options and solutions for the connection to an existing BMS

'BMS are responsible for controlling environmental and safety conditions in buildings by maintaining comfort and security levels within predefined limits according to recognised standards' [2]. Although mainly developed for control and comfort purposes, BMSs provide the opportunity to measure and improve energy efficiency as the existing infrastructure can be exploited for different energy efficiency actions. A BMS has the ability to collect and manage large amounts of data related to building management but, at the same time, a BMS has a limited capacity for analysing collected data from different points of view. This limited capacity in data analysis belongs mainly to the scope of the BMS that is limited to an efficient and effective plant management but is not designed to provide functionalities for the creation of flexible KPI (Key Performance Indicator) that can provide a wider image of the building behaviour.

As a consequence, it is absolutely mandatory to extract information from a BMS in order to analyse it under different perspectives.

Data collection from a BMS is complex to deal with. This is due to the fact that each BMS provider protects its software from replacement by other BMS providers. This situation usually brings a difficult path to find an optimal solution. BMSs can be classified in three levels depending on data accessibility, each of them representing an incremental degree of integration complexity:

- Easy access: in this case, an external/remote client can access the same data used by the BMS.
- Average access: in this case, there is no direct access to the data used by the BMS but a standard protocol is provided. An external client will have to access data through the BMS, i.e. the BMS will act as a data proxy. For instance, a typical solution incorporates a database in which the BMS stores all the data and the external software links to this database.
- Difficult access: this case is encountered when a proprietary protocol is used by the BMS. In this situation either the BMS provider is willing to cooperate and open its proprietary protocol or not. In the former case, it would be possible to program the data transfer to an external software while, in the latter case, the only solution is to try to interface directly to the field equipment.

From a technical point of view, several possible solutions can be used, the main difference being the level of independence of the interface from the BMS. In this context, independence is defined as "*the ability of the interface module to be transparent to internal modifications that can occur in the BMS during its life cycle*". Therefore, it is very complex to achieve total independence so we try to reduce the effort needed to maintain this kind of connectors. The effort reduction means that in those cases where the total independence from the BMS cannot be achieved, we will implement mechanisms, such as configuration files or intermediate data collection, as in the Challenger approach (see section 3.2), with the aim of reducing the maintenance effort during BMS and connector life cycle.

The following sub-sections describe the main options and solutions allowing the connection to an existing BMS and the data gathered by this kind of systems. Within each of the described solutions we will find different actors involved. Each actor has a particular level of commitment that characterizes the interface independence of the solution.

The most suitable connection methods are described in the following sub-sections.

2.1 Reading data via public API's

A software system can be defined as “*interoperable*” if it is able to share internally managed information with any external system. This feature is achieved internally defining a set of methods to share this information. API's represent the most suitable method to achieve this objective.

This method requires that the BMS exposes a set of documented API that can be invoked by external clients to have access to internal data. This approach is quite easy to implement and guarantees the necessary features to the external client. Additionally, it does not require a deep knowledge of the target system on the client side because the developer will deal with a set of documented functions to use. You get exactly what you need and any changes in the internal structure of the BMS will not be reflected in the external API definition, thus, not affecting the external clients that use it. If the API becomes obsolete, a new one will be provided by the BMS supplier and a small effort is normally required to update remote clients to adapt them to the new situation. A REST or SOAP server must be provided by the BMS provider to expose all required APIs. This communication is also fully synchronised with data generation because the external program can poll the data with the required frequency without affecting the BMS behaviour.

The BMS provider is involved in this communication process only during system design in order to define the datasets to be shared as well as the methods. The data consumer can gather available data having knowledge only of the API's requirements.

This approach is a win-win strategy because from the BMS provider side they can provide extra features to their customers with a limited effort and from the client side, in this case the Hit2Gap platform, a generic framework can be defined and subsequently adapted to different API sets in a very easy way.

The following picture describes the classic approach related to an API implementation

Figure 3. Typical API approach

The client side represent external BMS connector that query the BMS structure using the API Layer.

The involved actors and actions required are shown in table 1 in section 2.6.

2.2 Direct access to BMS Database

This approach looks a bit more complex to implement because it requires a deeper knowledge of the BMS internal structure and requires the use of SQL statements to prepare data queries. Any changes in the database structure must be reflected in a change to this query module having a more expensive maintenance. Basically, this method could be implemented with access rights to BMS given by the building manager without involving the BMS provider team. See the synthesis table 1 in section 2.6 to visualize the involved actors and actions required.

The involved actors and actions required are shown in table 1 in section 2.6.

This method can be implemented in two possible ways described below:

2.2.1 Direct access to operational data tables

In this case, the BMS manager, internal to the building managing staff, shares with the data consumer a description of the required tables and possible access methods (predefined queries). Direct access to operational tables guarantee that data stored in the BMS can be immediately available for external clients and can be collected at the most suitable rate. In this configuration, is the data consumer schedules data collection frequency, a parameter that can be modified dynamically on demand. Thus, if a KPI requires the modification of data flow rate depending on the quality of the result, this modification is under total control of the consumer by means of the data rate provided by the BMS. Of course, any change in the table structure (for instance in case of a new version of the BMS is deployed) could void the existing procedure and might require a large effort to restore the original functionalities.

Figure 4. Direct access to database table

2.2.2 Access to a buffer table

This second approach requires that the BMS manager, in charge of data collection, prepares a batch module to copy significant data to an “external” table that will be queried by the external client. In this case, any changes on the internal database structure will be managed by the BMS manager team and remains transparent to the external client. With this approach, even if data are accessed directly, data availability is strictly linked to the frequency of the data generated by the internal database. In HIT2GAP we use this approach to gather consumption data generated within the BMS system installed at Challenger pilot site (see section 3.2.6).

Figure 5. Data access via a buffer table

2.3 Batch Export of required data on disc files

This is probably one of the most common used methods. In fact, it does not require to grant any access to the internal structure of the BMS or to manage any kind of interface with the external world. The most common format for this kind of exported files are CSV or XML: the first one requires a document that describes the meaning of each exported value, the second one can be self-explanatory if it is exported using a suitable model. For this kind of communication, it is necessary to implement an FTP protocol to transfer the exported file to an area that can be accessed by the external client. Data availability is strictly linked to the export procedure and is very difficult to control it from the external program if data production configuration is not aligned. For instance, required frequency may not be aligned with the export process frequency. Mixing this method with calling an API that is in charge of data extraction and formatting can enable the data consumer to retrieve data at a variable rate. This method has low flexibility but is cheap to implement and maintain. In Challenger pilot site, we use this method to gather data collected by Build-Ax sensors that are not integrated in existing BMS (see section 3.2.8).

Figure 6. Data transfer on FTP server

2.4 Implement a specific protocol

Implementing a specific protocol means having a direct access to specific devices available in the monitored building. This approach normally takes place when we are in the case of a building without a BMS installed or we are dealing with new devices that are not yet integrated in the existing BMS.

This is a quite common approach because it does not require to create an interface with the BMS software and overtakes the most common interface problems.

This option can be implemented through two different configurations:

- The BMS provider delivers a protocol specification to be used in order to have access to the internal network and gives all necessary credentials. The external client can define the necessary query rate and gather only the necessary information.
- If a set of new devices must be added to the building and cannot be integrated, or it is time-consuming to integrate them in the BMS. It is possible to implement the device protocol and directly manage these devices without any access to the BMS. Naturally this approach requires to maintain the protocol interface in accordance with any upgrade that can occur in the physical device. In many cases, also standard protocols require some customization to fit the implementation made by the hardware provider.

The complexity of the implementation will depend on the following characteristics of the protocol:

- **Open or proprietary:** A protocol is open when the creator of the protocol provides the specification openly, with no restrictions. Proprietary protocols make the protocols restricted to the creator of the device and do not share the specification.
- **Standard:** A standard protocol requires all parties, from developers to end-users, to agree on a specification that can be implemented on their respective devices.
- **Interoperability:** A protocol is interoperable when a component from one vendor can be replaced with a component from a different vendor.

Figure 7. Specific protocol to access BMS external devices

2.5 Direct access to BMS counter devices

This is the most difficult option to implement because it requires to have access rights to the network gateways that manage the different types of sensors belonging to the BMS installation. It is possible to implement different protocols (i.e. MODBUS/IP, BACNET, SNMP traps etc.) that are in charge of querying the devices for collecting data and, eventually, send actuation commands back to the devices. This method is highly invasive and must be implemented if no data collection is made by the BMS, so data can be transmitted only in real time and no external access to the physical network is available. Basically this option totally bypasses the BMS controlling procedure. However, it requires direct access to the BMS internal network.

Figure 8. Access to BMS device via internal supported protocol

2.6 Synthesis and discussions

The following table summarises the identified solutions and highlights the most important criteria and decision-making elements that should be considered within the selection of the connection solution.

Table 1: Comparison between different interfacing methods

Existing solutions	Requirements	Stakeholder	Advantages	Drawbacks
Reading data via public API's	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BMS supplier must expose a set of APIs as a basic feature. Data consumer must have details on API call and be aware on service availability. Data Consumer need access credentials 	<p>Data consumer</p> <p>Building manager</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No actions are requested from BMS producer since He provides APIs end-points. Changes in API can be managed at low cost Data can be 	No evidence of significant drawback

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BMS provider must maintain this set of APIs synched with any improvement or change in BMS functionalities. 		consumed in almost real time.	
Direct access to BMS Database	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BMS supplier must provide a description of internal tables. BMS provider must define protection policies on non-open data. Data consumer must have a dedicated path to access data securely. 	BMS supplier Building manager	This method is faster in accessing the data and can be easily tailored to data consumer requests without specific development on BMS provider side. Data collection is made via SQL query. Data consumer can decide when execute the query (data capture rate).	Data consumer must be aware of any changes that will occur in the DB tables.
Batch Export of required data on disc files	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BMS manager must provide a description file data record BMS manager must provide a location where data files can be collected Data consumer must develop a specific data parser. 	BMS manager Data consumer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Any changes that take place at the BMS side is potentially transparent to data consumer. The data interface is easy to maintain 	The data consumer cannot modify data rate export accordingly with his necessity, and is linked to BMS manager scheduling.
Implement a specific protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data consumer collects from hardware manufacturer technical information on protocol implementation Building manager must provide hardware connectivity and new sensors deployment 	Data consumer Hardware sensor manufacturer Building manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No interface with BMS is required. Save time and expenses necessary to integrate new sensors in the BMS. No impact on BMS operation. Typically is used in mixed interfacing 	Changes in hardware protocol implementation may need modification at software protocol implementation level.

	accordingly with building monitoring requests.		approach with other interface.	
Direct access to BMS counter devices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data consumer must be aware of available protocols implemented by BMS communication. BMS provider must communicate the structure of inner registry to access data. 	Data consumer BMS provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct counter access enables data consumer to configure data collection rate as needed. No overhead due to go thru BMS procedure. 	Normally BMS provider do not agree in opening this information for external actors.

3 Overview of HIT2GAP pilots data sources

The aim of this section is to describe, for each pilot site, the existing possible data sources in order to introduce the following discussion on existing and retained method to collect the data. Therefore the section focuses on the basic information available for each pilot sites with the aim to describe in a concise way how each pilot site can operate to expose its information to the HIT2GAP modules.

3.1 NUIG Galway

3.1.1 Brief Pilot site description

The demonstration site is the New Engineering Building located at National University of Ireland, Galway, Ireland. The building was opened on the 15th of July 2011.

The site is mainly a teaching and research facility with offices, classrooms, laboratories and workshops.

One of the main themes of the NUIG Engineering Building is that it is a "Living Laboratory" for students. This means that the structure, systems and operation of the building is revealed and utilised as a teaching tool and students are allowed to access data for observation and analysis.

Another theme of the building is that it was constructed and commissioned with emphasis on minimising the impact to the environment. This is reflected in the commissioning of solar collectors, a biomass boiler, heat exchangers and other green technologies to set an example for students, who will eventually go on to propagate a green philosophy as alumni of the University.

3.1.2 Sub-Systems available

The building consists of 14,250 m² spread across 4 floors. There is a district heating system feeding the nearby sports centre and swimming pool. The number of occupants is estimated at 1100 students and 110 staff.

The Climatic Zone is cool temperate. Galway has a year-round mild, moist, temperate and changeable climate, due to the prevailing winds of the North Atlantic Current

The electrical contract consists of lighting, general services, fire alarm & voice evacuation, hearing aid induction loop, intruder alarm, access control system, CCTV video surveillance system.

Power is supplied from the ESB network (electricity provider) via the Medium Voltage switchgear, transformer, main board (energy centre) and from there to a sub-board on each floor (on the east and west side of the building on the ground, first, second and third floor)

Heating systems consist of a CHP (Combined Heat and Power) system, 3 gas boilers and a pellet biomass boiler.

Lighting systems consist of low energy lighting with presence and lux level lighting controls including manual switching; Lux dipping throughout the day and night (the computer drops the lights if it is

bright, and lowers the levels at night); LED Exit Signs and emergency lighting; External LED Lighting with time-clock and photocell control.

Ventilation systems consist of Air Handling Units, natural stack ventilation, climate wall with top-vented stack control and solar control via blinds.

There is a weather station present on the roof of the building. Data from this weather station is also collected and stored in the database.

A detailed description of the pilot site is provided in D5.1 [3] D5.1 “Report on energy monitoring data collection for an initial assessment of the pilot sites”, HIT2GAP deliverable, February 2017.

[4] D5.2 “HIT2GAP prototype implementation report”, HIT2GAP deliverable, May 2018.

[5] D5.3 “Effects brought by the HIT2GAP solution in all three pilot sites (results Evaluation) and overall evaluation of the HIT2GAP solution”, HIT2GAP deliverable, August 2019.

]. There are ten communications controllers (UC32.Net controllers) on site. They can have up to 254 field controllers each. The BMS has a weather monitoring station, with weather sensors logging data. Data from the pilot site is to be collected and transmitted to HIT2GAP for analysis. Data collection will be achieved via an Aspect BMS.

3.1.3 List of collected data

Timestamped value pairs per datalog will be collected. Depending on the datalog type (e.g. cumulative, scaled etc.), some post processing may be applied. The raw data and processed data will be collected and stored in Aspect Energy. In addition to physical datalogs, virtual datalog values may also be computed.

For each zone, the following data will be collected and stored in a MYSQL database:

- Electricity energy data collected from the cumulative total meters for each zone
- Water data collected from the mains water usage meter in the engineering building.
- Gas data collected from the CHP usage meter and the boilers usage meter
- Indoor environmental conditions: mainly temperature; however, humidity and CO₂ are available for in some areas
- Setpoints
- Valve control signals

This data will be stored at fifteen minute intervals on the field controllers. However, this data will be polled more frequently, for example at one minute intervals for use in the Simulation module by Aspect Energy and pushed to the MYSQL database.

It is assumed that the raw collected data of physical datalogs will be forwarded to HIT2GAP only, but the format, protocol, and frequency of this transmission has yet to be defined. It is also assumed that an initial configuration step to configure datalogs in HIT2GAP will be required. It is unclear whether this step will be a manual administration task, or an integration task.

It is assumed that Cylon Controls Ltd (CYL) is not responsible for the integrity of data collected from the pilot site, NUIG. Collection of data should begin in 2016. This collection will be monitored by CYL, who will report missing data to NUIG at their earliest convenience.

The energy data for baseline establishment was collected in the following ways:

- The electricity energy data was collected from bills provided by the building services office
- The water data was collected from the mains water usage meter in the engineering building.
- The gas data has been collected from the CHP usage meter and the boilers usage meter.

The baseline electricity data is available in an excel sheet. The baseline water and gas data is stored in a MySQL database that the BMS previously logged to.

3.1.4 List of existing protocols and data connectors

As the BMS provider of the pilot site is CYL, the communication protocol is IP (to the UC32.Net) and Unitron (from the UC32.Net to the Field and Unitary Controllers).

As part of the CYL supervisor software Command Centre, the CYL Reports software archives datalogs on the CYL BMS controllers to an SQL database.

During the site audit, it was noted that there are a number of Schneider Modbus devices on site. Integration with these devices falls outside the scope of this project.

3.1.5 Connectivity Schema

3.1.5.1 Directly from the BMS Controllers

The log values can be accessed directly from the controllers that contain them using the CYL Datalog Manager. The CYL Datalog Manager allows the user to view datalogs or export the datalogs to a comma separated file (csv).

This method will only allow the user to extract the log samples that are currently on the controller, i.e. the last 1024 samples.

3.1.5.2 Directly from the SQL Database

On the BMS machine, there are two SQL databases. One database contains data from November 2015 to early January 2016. The second database has data from June 2014 to October 2015. There is also a large backup of an SQL database that contains older data.

These databases can be accessed through the SQL management studio and SQL queries can be executed to obtain the desired information as illustrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Example of sql query

The query used in the above case is shown below:

```

SELECT  [Datalog Descriptors].[Datalog Name], [Datalog Values].Time, [Datalog
        Values].Value
FROM    [Datalog Descriptors] INNER JOIN
        [Datalog Values] ON [Datalog Descriptors].[Datalog ID] = [Datalog
        Values].[Datalog ID]
WHERE   ([Datalog Descriptors].[Datalog Name] = N'AHU103 Sched Enable')
    
```

Queries can be written to obtain and present data in the desired format.

3.1.5.3 Overall objective

Aspect Energy is a SaaS product which will be developed as part of the HIT2GAP engagement. It will analyse energy data captured from the NUIG pilot site, and provide some supervision capability for the target site remotely. This system, and its peripherals, will integrate with the HIT2GAP platform. The system will be comprised of a RESTful API which will expose Aspect Energy services over (secure) HTTP, and will typically consume and return JSON. Most services will require authentication, which will be achieved using a central authentication service. A user interface will be accessible via modern web browsers, with some intelligence to reconfigure the screens depending on the accessing device (e.g. mobile, tablet, desktop computer). Multi-tenancy is achieved at the application layer, so logged in users will only have access to their own data. Modules, and features therein, will be accessible to users depending on their role (user, admin, super-user).

Aspect Energy will maintain a mapping for a HIT2GAP model relative to its native model for a datalog, meter, or point.

The pilot site may have a native Aspect BMS, from which data can be shared with Aspect Energy directly.

A distributed message queue is used for interaction between back end modules. The figure below shows the architecture of how CYL extracts data from real world sites, and stores this and forwards data to the HIT2GAP platform. Aspect Energy will retrieve data from the HIT2GAP platform using an embedded web service client.

Giving the previous statement we decided to feed the HIT2GAP platform database directly from the NUIG BMS instead of using PLAT.ONE interface, with this choice we want to demonstrate the ability of the platform to be fed from different sources using different data path.

Figure 10. Data extraction schema for HIT2GAP platform

During the course of the project, the BMS machine that hosts CYL supervisor software Command Centre will continue to run in parallel with the developments of the HIT2GAP project.

As part of the developments mentioned above, CYL will install a number of Aspect devices on site. As a temporary measure until the HIT2GAP platform is developed, these devices will push their logged BMS data to an Amazon Web Service Relational Database Service (AWS RDS). CYL will also create a RESTful web-service with basic authentication to GET data directly from the AWS RDS with NUIG data, and host them. As CYL will be hosting the data, any charges incurred as a result of partner interaction with the data will be passed on.

Agreements:

- Null values should be sent for missing data
- Raw data only is to be sent (not aggregated for instance)
- Not rounded format as much as reasonably considered
- CYL data is one minute data; it will be sent at a **configurable** frequency (e.g. every 15 minutes)
- Scalability/load balancing should be considered as part of HIT2GAP platform
- If data cannot be sent, or is unsuccessfully sent, CYL will resend data
- Authentication is required

3.2 Challenger

3.2.1 Brief Pilot site description

Challenger, Bouygues Construction's head office, was constructed in 1998 and refurbished from 2011 to 2014. There are three main buildings in Challenger that cover a total area of 65000 m²: the central atrium, the North Triangle (NT) and the South Triangle (ST). The site is awarded triple certification (HQE®, LEED® and BREEAM®) confirming the very high level of environmental quality achieved by the entirely renovated building, mainly thanks to the installation of 25,000 m² of photovoltaic panels, 300 m² of hybrid thermal/photovoltaic panels, 75 geothermal sensors and a geothermal doublet, as well as to 24,000 m² of ventilated double-skin facade incorporating an automatic blind. Almost all technical equipment are piloted by an assembled BMS with Omron controller and PCVue SCADA software.

The site is mainly occupied by the employees of Bouygues Construction and hence it consists mainly of offices distributed on open space areas, small offices and meeting rooms. The building also includes a multifunctional room, a video projection room, a sport gym, a company restaurant, a banking agency, a hairdresser and a shop.

HIT2GAP is mainly being implemented on the NT and ST which have 4 floor levels and 1 basement level.

3.2.2 Sub-Systems available

The BMS installed on site has three layers: a supervision layer of brand ARC Informatique and model PcVue, an automation layer of brand Omron and a field layer consisting of the different sensors along with PLC (Programmable Logic Controller) inputs/outputs. The PcVue software is proprietary. PLC inputs/outputs, automated controller and supervision are connected on the same TCP/IP network. Smart sensors send their information thanks to PLC inputs/outputs to automated controller, which uses these ones to monitor energy equipment. Automated controller also communicates with Supervision layer to send sensor's data and to receive control command. The BMS system manages all building areas and systems.

Consumption data can be available each 10 minutes and are stored into an SQL database.

The installation of this system was finalized in 2014.

There are several energy sources installed on site:

- Ground source energies: dry and wet probe
- Photovoltaics
- Thermal solar energy
- Electricity grid
- Thermal generators (only used as back- up).

The systems managed by the BMS are:

- Production of Heat and Cold
- Distribution of Heat and Cold
- Ventilation and Air conditioning units
- Air Handling Units

- Domestic Hot Water (DHW) production
- General Electricity Metering
- Energy Metering
- Water distribution
- Indoor and Outdoor Lighting management
- Electrical fault detection system
- Sprinkler fire system
- Flood detection system

3.2.3 List of collected data

There are 36900 data collected by the BMS system in Challenger including:

- All energy consumption data by zone, floor or building,
- Indoor environmental conditions: mainly temperature; however, luminosity, humidity and CO₂ are available for specific areas,
- Setpoints,
- Valve control signals,
- Alarms,
- Leakages.

The data stored by the SQL database includes 1296 measurement points consisting of all the consumption data by zone, floor and building and will be available to HIT2GAP through Plat.One. These data are collected by the BMS every 10 minutes to every 1 hour depending on the meter.

PLAT.ONE will read Thermal and Electrical Energy consumption data from a buffer table including consumption data of 389 meters (North Triangle (160), South Triangle (161) and 68 from the Main Building).

3.2.4 List of existing protocols and data connectors

The communication protocol in the field level consists of:

- KNX TP for office blinding management
- Modbus/RS485 for groundwater Heat pump
- M.Bus and Bacnet/ IP for thermal metering
- ModBus RS485 for electricity metering

All these field protocols or buses which are besides the metering system will be converted into Profinet TCP/Ethernet in automation level with Omron controller, and the metering system will be concentrated by ModbusTCP/IP.

3.2.5 Connectivity Schema

The following figure describes the architecture of the building automation and controls system installed in the Challenger site and describes different protocols available as listed in previous section 3.2.4.

Figure 11. Building Automation & Control System Architecture of Challenger site

3.2.6 Connection with PLAT.ONE:

Data acquisition deals with energy consumption data coming from different energy meters distributed in several electrical cabinets and technical rooms on the site. All this information is collected into a common table into the Challenger database.

The structure of the metering network is fix and doesn't change. The basic information about this network (Unique id of the counter, counter location, type of measure, measure scale, description etc...) has been provided via an Excel file (see Table 2).

We proceed by executing an initial load of the network structure, creating nodes in PLAT.ONE with their own measures, cross-referencing with the final version of the excel file modified with the English translation of French wording.

At a specified time interval the measure value will be gathered from the interface table using a time stamp range.

Data that belongs to nodes not created during network initial load will be ignored.

Table 2: List of fields describing meter information to be used for initial load

Column name	Usage
Address	Primary key to access data and to uniquely identify the node in the network
UoM	Unit of measure
Scale	Scale to be applied to the read data
Building	Building name (TN, TS, BATE)
Level	Floor Level within the building
Zone	Zone within the level
N.Meter	Identification code of the meter
Equipment Counted	Description of the equipment

- Each node will have a measured value linked to it.
- The initial load will generate 160 nodes from TN Building, 161 nodes from TS Building, 68 nodes from the main and technical buildings for a total of 389 meters; each node will be created with its Position and Measure attributes (as shown in Figure 12).

Figure 12. Node property as shown in PLAT.ONE

- The type of measure collected is determined by the information stored into the Excel file provided by Challenger FM Manager.
- Since the identification information are static and are not provided with the collected value, we decided to store this information as “Custom properties” linked to the node (see Figure 13).

Nodes-Custom Properties|NSAP: 0.0.0.2 ID:4338

Custom Properties

Tools

Property Name	Value	Del	Del
UsedScale	0,01		
Floor	PK		
Uom	m3		
Zone	21		
Building	TS		
N° Meter	CPT-TS-PK-1		
Name SQL table	DIRISCHAL_EMN_50304_...		
Equipment Counted	heat pump 01 & 02 Volume		

Figure 13. List of custom property describing meter attributes

To collect real time data we have access to the table VIZ_T_VIZELIA_COMPTEUR where the data coming from the different meters in TN, TS and the technical production rooms is stored. The data collection is executed by a configurable SQL-Statement that will be executed periodically directly from the Challenger database.

This table contains a column named “Address” that represent the primary key to get the consumption value from the meters, this primary key will match with the values contained into column M.

The column “Value” contain an integer value representing the measure, this value must be scaled using the value stored in column O. Please note that the measures value stored into the database are already scaled applying the scale factor. The column “Timestamp” is a date time field.

3.2.7 Validation test on data

Following the data reading protocol, we realized a test environment whit the aim of expose all data collected within an easy to navigate web dashboard.

This dashboard provides three different tabs showing each a grid with the list of existing meters belonging to each building with all properties and the last value available. By clicking on any meter in the lower part of the page, the related values are displayed on a selected time scale, by default current day, which can be changed as needed.

Figure 14. Data Visualization Dashboard as collected into PLAT.ONE

3.2.8 BuildAx sensors - API for connectivity of BuildAx solution and HIT2GAP platform

A set of BuildAx sensors has been deployed at Challenger pilot site with the aim to collect environmental data in an area of the TS building.

Actually, the information collected by these sensors are not available through the Challenger BMS system but it is planned to integrate this type of sensors in HIT2GAP through PLAT.ONE in order to provide a connection port available for all pilot sites that requires to deploy this kind of sensors.

The data will be accessed via an API provided by UOS that follows the schema described into the next paragraph. Please note that, at the moment, we have not yet defined the detailed data flow rate.

BuildAx ENV sensors in a range up to 300m are connected wirelessly to local BuildAx LRS (Logger, Router, Server). BuildAx LRS stores measurements and provides means to fetch data via internet if the LRS is connected using its Ethernet port.

HIT2GAP platform (or middleware applications such as Plat.One) can retrieve data from BuildAx LRS using the LINUX/UNIX command entget (see Appendix 1, section 7.1.4).

In this case we implement a mixed method to collect data from sensors:

- Using API provided by UOS that query the datalogger connect to the sensors network and generate a CSV file.
- File transfer and parsing to read data persisted into the datalogger and send them to PLAT.ONE

Data will be collected from the datalogger when needed selecting a certain time interval.

In order to create a set of continuous data the PLAT.ONE connector will send data request at a defined time interval, i.e. each 30 minutes, and stores this data into PLAT.ONE managing the appropriate sensor node.

Any time the connector read the data check the sensor id against the list of existing sensors and provide to:

- Create a new node and store received measure linked to this node

Or

- Add the new measure to the existing node

With this approach HIT2GAP platform can collect data in a seamless mode setting, for each query, the most appropriate time interval and choosing the whole set of nodes or a specific one. As we do for BMS data also these sensors data will displayed in the web dashboard in order to validate them.

3.3 NanoGUNE

3.3.1 Brief Pilot site description

The demonstration site is the NanoGUNE building located at San Sebastián, Spain. The building was opened in 2008.

NanoGUNE is a research center with the mission of performing world-class nanoscience research for the competitive growth of the Basque Country. The site is mainly a research facility with offices and laboratories with clean rooms.

The demonstration site is composed of two buildings named “tower” and “nano building”, both buildings are connected by the ground floor. The tower have 5 floors with offices and the nano building have 3 floors with 15 laboratories and open offices.

3.3.2 Sub-Systems available

The building is approximately 7.300 m² and is located in a mesothermal climate, moderate in terms of temperatures, and rainy. It is called humid temperate climate without dry season, or Atlantic climate.

The heat production is based on 2 natural gas boilers producing hot water with a total power of 462 kW, the boilers produce heat for air conditioning and sanitary hot water

For cooling production the building has a chiller of 1,235 kW with heat recovery, this chiller produces cold water for HVAC and for the cooling laboratory’s devices.

The air conditioning system has seven air conditioners and numerous fan coils distributed throughout the building. In addition to nanoGUNE there are 16 air handler unit for the laboratories and an air handler unit for the clean room.

The lighting is mainly fluorescent and halogen technology. All the lighting of the installation is controlled by a centralized KNX system where it’s possible to see if the lighting is on or off and it’s possible to control.

3.3.3 List of collected data

The data collected by the BMS are listed below:

- Lighting status by zones.
- 18 thermal meters with the following information:
 - Instant consumption of cooling / heating energy
 - Total consumption of cooling / heating energy
 - Temperature
 - Flow
- 43 electrical meters with the following information:
 - Intensity: Intensity Per phase
 - Voltage: Voltage Phase to phase, Phase to neutral
 - Power:
- Active power, Per phase, Three phase total
- Reactive power, Per phase, Three phase total
- Apparent power, Per phase, Three phase total
 - Energy
- Active
- Reactive
- Apparent
 - Minimum and maximum values
- Min / Max voltage L-L
- Min / Max voltage L-N
- Data of the HVAC system:
 - Ambient temperature of rooms.
 - Temperature of heating and cooling circuits.
 - Ambient temperature setpoints.
 - Status of fan coils fans.
 - Pressure switch alarms.
 - On / off status of circulation pumps and air conditioners, boilers and chiller.

3.3.4 List of existing protocols and data connectors

Currently in the building, there are two SCADA systems with totally different functions in terms of use and capacity.

On one hand, there is the ITACE 500 Webserver based on Siemens technology that collects all the control signals of the building's air conditioning part and also allows the control of the fan coils of the building, although in a very discrete and limited way.

Figure 15. Building Automation & Controls System Architecture of nanoGUNE site

This system is based on LON technology for the field control elements finishing in a superior architecture in BACNET / LON bus and dying the whole system in a gateway PXG80-N that converts those protocols to BACNET-IP. The Itace 500 software is fed through an IP connection to the PXG80-N router of all the display information of all the readings from the probes and sensors of the installation, as well as the rest of field and actuation elements.

On the other hand, the software BMS NETx Automation manages the control part of lighting and of the thermal and electrical consumption.

Figure 16. High level schema of NETx system

Figure 17. Connection schema on KNX back bone infrastructure

From the SCADA NETx Automation, all KNX protocol-based lighting is controlled and all thermometer counters and electrical network analysers in the system are monitored and recorded.

3.3.5 Connectivity Schema

Scada NETx Automation records the historical data of thermal meters and electrical analysers in a SQL database. In addition to saving the data in a SQL database, they have a license of the MARS application also has the ability to generate reports, depending on the data recorded in that database. This database is saved on the PC with the management system and is fully accessible through any standard database manager.

In the case of the ITACE 500 web server, it doesn't have the possibility to register the values of the sensors, setpoints ... in a SQL database. Through the web pages, you can configure the different points and display the records in text mode. As the two systems communicate via IP Bacnet, it is possible to send the data by bus from Siemens to Scada NETx Automation and register them in their SQL database.

3.3.6 Retained communication method

In this pilot site, it is expected to install MM-WSN sensors as a means for collecting information actually not available without the need to integrate these sensors in the BMS operating on this site. Considering that this kind of sensors could be used in other pilot sites, the description on how HIT2GAP integrates them is described in Appendix 1 and is basically valid for any application of this technology. Further details on the deployment of these sensors will be explained this will be explained in detail in deliverables D5.2 [4] and D5.3 [5].

Since the actual installed system cannot be accessed neither directly using the existing webserver nor with direct access, we agreed with the system manager to provide the measures, listed in section 3.3.3 of this document, using a CSV file. This file will contain daily measurement and will be deployed on a FTP server on a daily basis. The PLAT.ONE connector will automatically detect the new file deployed and provide the necessary actions to load incoming data.

As the sensor network mapped into the CSV file is fixed, we can create the sensor network, as we do with Challenger meters, reading once an Excel file containing the basic information of each node and storing them into network topology.

The following table shows an example of the incoming network structure:

Table 3: Network structure for connected sensors

	D.B	MODEL METER	IP ADDRESS
		LSS100100	10.227.126.203
MAINS	NPre General Red	PM810	
	NPre CPD	A9MEM3255	10.227.126.190
	NPre Planta Sótano Torre 1	A9MEM3255	
	NPre Planta Primera Torre 1	A9MEM3255	
	NPre Planta Quinta Torre 1	A9MEM3255	
	NPre Planta Segunda Nano	A9MEM3255	
GENERATOR	Pre General Grupo	PM810	

	Pre Montacargas	A9MEM3255	10.227.126.191
	Pre Planta Sótano Laboratorio	A9MEM3255	
	Pre Planta Baja	A9MEM3255	
	Pre Clean Room	A9MEM3255	
	Pre Planta Sótano Torre 1	A9MEM3255	
	Pre Planta Primera Torre 1	A9MEM3255	
	Pre Planta Quinta Torre 1	A9MEM3255	
	Pre Planta Segunda Nano	A9MEM3255	
	Pre Extracción Parking	A9MEM3255	
UPS	SAI General SAI	PM2230	10.227.126.191
	SAI Planta Sótano Laboratorio	A9MEM3255	
	SAI Planta Baja	A9MEM3255	
	SAI Planta Primera Torre 1	A9MEM3255	
	SAI Planta Quinta Torre 1	A9MEM3255	
	SAI CPD	A9MEM3255	

3.4 Wilanow Town Hall

3.4.1 Brief Pilot site description

This Pilot site is located in Warsaw (POLAND), it is a public building owned by the City of Warsaw. It is totally dedicated to offices of 12406 m² (with garage) divided in two buildings, and consisting of 3 floors, a grand floor and an underground garage. The building is not permanently occupied. The building is a new construction (2014). As energy sources, it uses the district heating network and electricity (4 chillers for cooling). The BMS (SATCONTROL) manages lighting (DALI system), air conditioning, ventilation, indoor temperature. Unfortunately the SATCONTROL system doesn't allow to collect the data, but only to display information coming from the field into a dashboard used to control the system. Currently a BMS improvement plan is being prepared in order to provide some capabilities in data management. Renewable energies available at the site consists of heat recovery ventilation.

3.4.2 Sub-Systems available

Currently the BMS system implemented in the Wilanów Town Hall (buildings A and B) does not fit into the HIT2GAP concept. An extension/upgrade of the system will take place soon. The Main feature that has to be implemented is the data acquisition tool, which is missing and will be added. The core of the system will be a WAGO PLC controller, which will collect data from the devices implemented in the building and data from public weather station. Two alternative software solutions are being taken into account one based on a free web application developed by WAGO and the other based on a SCADA system named Asix4WAGO, developed by ASKOM. The second solution is much more powerful and offers lots of tools for trends analysis, programming advanced schedules and has very neat user interface allowing for easy configuration of many different screens. Asix4WAGO uses SQL database for data storing and can write data with high resolution (less than one second) if needed.

The subsystems that are meant to be connected to the BMS are:

- Heat metering (building A+B and 3rd floor in building A)
- Cold metering (building A+B and 3rd floor in building A)
- Electricity metering (building A+B and 3rd floor in building A)
- Air handling units (only unit supplying 2nd and 3rd floor in building A)
- Air conditioning units (only at 3rd floor in building A)
- Cold production units (building A only)
- Indoor lighting metering (3rd floor in building A only)
- Indoor CO₂ metering (3rd floor in building A only)
- Indoor motion sensors (3rd floor in building A only)
- Indoor temperature and humidity (3rd floor in building A only)

3.4.3 List of collected data

Currently BMS does not collect data. All data on energy consumption are based on invoices.

3.4.4 List of existing protocols and data connectors

The following table lists the existing connection protocols that are used to transmit data to the system dashboard. However, they cannot be used for gathering data toward the HIT2GAP platform. We expect that the implementation of the new BMS system will open a MODBUS/IP channel to gather the data.

Table 4: List of devices connected to the actual BMS with related protocol

List of connected devices	
Central computer	LAN (Local Area Network)
Switch 16 port	Modbus IP
Switch 32 port	Modbus IP
Thermostat	Modbus RTU or Modbus IP
Electricity meter	Modbus RTU
Heat meter	Modbus RTU
Fancoil	Modbus
Lighting	DALI protocol

3.4.5 Retained communication protocol

For this pilot site, the retained connection protocol is MODBUS/IP as described in paragraph 3.4.5.1. We will add further details to the Data Agreement protocol document once the specific protocol is agreed with the pilot site responsible.

Currently, the BMS situation of the Warsaw pilot site is not completely defined due to the deployment of a new software in the incoming months. For the meantime, it was decided, with the pilot site responsible and the BMS provider, that the data collection will be executed via a MODBUS/IP protocol that will be deployed in order to interface the BMS.

In the following section the basic information about this protocol usage within PLAT.ONE is described.

3.4.5.1 ModBus/IP communication requirements

A Modbus/IP communication protocol acts in client/server configuration, the server side exposes data coming from the sensors and the client side will send data requests.

In order to access information from the client side, the IP and PORT address of the server must be available to configure the communication.

The PLAT.ONE Modbus/IP interface is able to:

- allow retrieval of data from multiple devices on a TCP network
- allow the selection of data items that will be represented in Plat-One among the entirety of items available on the device

A configuration file drives this communication. The file describes both server access information and data to be retrieved from the server.

Modbus protocol do not describe the data types of the information stored in its registers; meaning that we cannot separate a temperature from power consumption value by simply reading the data from the server. To be able to recognize and separate each different measure, we define in PLAT.ONE a data model that describes this information and, using the configuration files, creates the correspondence between data and information.

In order to activate a Modbus/IP connector the following information must be available:

- The IP address and port of Modbus server.
- A description of the Modbus registry available at the BMS output
- Data string format
- Meaning of each separate field in the string
- Number of registry available from the server

Note that if multiple servers are available, these information must be available for each server.

In section 7.1.5 an example of PLAT.ONE configuration file can be found (for more information see <http://docs.platone.io/wiki/DoryModbus>).

4 Conclusions

During the activities that took place in Task 2.2, as expected, we have dealt with different approaches for data sharing. These approaches require the use of different methods to fit specific needs.

For each pilot site, we have identified the most suitable technology to achieve our target “Collecting and normalizing data” to be exposed for HIT2GAP database where all modules will have access to query the necessary information.

At the moment we implement different data connectors that have been tailored to the different situations that we faced, more information will be available in deliverables D5.2 [4] and D5.3 [5].

Table 5: List of retained communication protocol for each Pilot Site

<i>Pilot Site/Data source</i>	<i>Connectors protocol</i>	<i>Sensor Data Frequency</i>	<i>Data collection</i>
Challenger	Direct SQL query	10 min.	Continuous
NanoGune	CSV File	5 min.	Daily via FTP
Wilanow	MODBUS/IP	15 min.	Continuous
MM-WSN	MQTT	30 min. (parametric)	Continuous
Indoor Positioning	REST Server	1 min. (parametric)	Continuous
Build-AX	REST Client/CSV File	10 min.	Hourly (defined at connector side)
NUIG	CSV File from datalog	To be defined	Continuous
NUIG	Direct SQL query	To be defined	Continuous

For each connector, a web dashboard has been implemented with the aim to provide a simple tool to check the incoming data before these data will be available to HIT2GAP platform. For the moment three dashboards are already available through a web interface and can be accessed by all the consortium partners. We report examples of these interfaces in paragraphs 3.2.7, 7.1.1.2, 7.1.3.4. The remaining dashboards that are not yet released will be described in deliverable D5.2 [4].

During this task, it became evident that a flexible environment for data collection, able to expose several connection methods, is crucial to achieve the target of flexibility and data capacity that HIT2GAP must obtain.

Basically such an environment, in this case PLAT.ONE, will offer this opportunity as shown in this document.

5 References

[1] D2.2 “Synthesis report on the benchmark conducted in the field of new data fields in offices – What is currently feasible?”, HIT2GAP deliverable, December 2016.

[2] Raymond Sterling Garay, ‘Self-Aware Buildings - An evaluation framework and implementation technologies for improving building operations’, PhD thesis submitted in May 2015.

[3] D5.1 “Report on energy monitoring data collection for an initial assessment of the pilot sites”, HIT2GAP deliverable, February 2017.

[4] D5.2 “HIT2GAP prototype implementation report”, HIT2GAP deliverable, May 2018.

[5] D5.3 “Effects brought by the HIT2GAP solution in all three pilot sites (results Evaluation) and overall evaluation of the HIT2GAP solution”, HIT2GAP deliverable, August 2019.

6 Glossary and acronyms

ABO	ABO DATA
API	Application Programming Interface
BACNET	Building Automation and Control Network
BACNET/IP	Building Automation and Control Network over IP
BACNET/LON	Building Automation and Control Network over Local Operating Network
BES	Bouygues Energies & Services
BMS	Building Management System
CANBUS	Controller Area Network Bus
CCTV	Closed Circuit Television
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
CYL	Cylon Controls
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DALI	Digital Addressable Lighting Interface
DOA	Description of the action
EU	European Union
EUR	EURECAT
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
H2G	HIT2GAP
HTTP	HyperText Transfer Protocol
HVAC	Heating, ventilation and air conditioning
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LAN	Local Area Network
LED	Light Emitting Diode
LON	Local Operating Network
LRS	Logger, Router, Server
MODBUS	Serial communication protocol
MODBUS/IP	Serial communication protocol over TCP/IP
MODBUS/RTU	Serial communication protocol with Remote Terminal Unit
MODBUS/RS485	Serial communication protocol on serial 485
MOS	Mostostal
MQTT	MQ Telemetry Transport
MM	Multi Measure
NBK	Nobatek
NT	North Triangle
NUIG	National University of Ireland Galway
PORT	Logical communication for TCP/IP protocol
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
PROFINET	Process Field Net
REST	Representational state transfer
SCADA	Supervisory control and data acquisition
SOAP	Simple Object Access Protocol
SNMP	Simple Network Management Protocol
SQL	Structured Query Language
ST	South Triangle
TCP/IP	Transmission Control Protocol/internet protocol
TEK	IK4-Tekniker
UOS	University Of Strathclyde
WP	Work-Package

WSN
XML

Wireless Sensor Network
eXtensible Markup Language

7 Appendices

7.1 Appendix 1: HIT2GAP Data Agreement

This Annex describes the technical specification for data collection from those data sources that do not belong to a specific pilot site but could be present in more than one pilot site. These data sources are connected to HIT2GAP via PLAT.ONE services.

7.1.1 INDOOR POSITIONING SYSTEM

This module will gather data from mobile devices to detect their position within a certain building. Position information will be gathered at a certain frequency rate that will be tuned during the test phase in order to manage the appropriate amount of data.

The information collected by this module are summarized in Table 6.

Table 6: Application Data produced by the Indoor positioning system

Name	Unit	Data Type	Description
Device_id	N/A	INT16	Represents the smartphone, smartwatch id
ts	N/A	UINT16	Time stamp tagging the collect data
Positions		String array	Collects a sequence of position information sent by the device at a certain time stamp
date	N/A	UINT16	Measuring time stamp (UTC format)
Lat	N/A	UINT16	Latitude of the device
Lng	N/A	UINT16	Longitude of the device
Alt	N/A	UINT16	Altitude or floor level
Type	N/A	String	Technology used to calculate position. Possible values : ble, wifi, wifi ble
Site	N/A	String	Id of the site

7.1.1.1 Used method for collecting Data

PLAT.ONE will gather the data by exposing a REST web service exchanging information using JSON format (see example below). PLAT.ONE will act as a server.

Example:

```
{
  "ts":1461838525,
  "device_id":"ZX1D22THKP",
  "positions":
  [
    {
      "site":28,
```

```
        "date":1461838523,
        "alt":1,
        "lng":2.1254145254625243,
        "lat":41.4890625155512,
        "type":"ble"
    },
    {
        "site":28,
        "date":1461838524,
        "alt":1,
        "lng":2.1254145057983878,
        "lat":41.48906255936378,
        "type":"ble"
    },
    {
        "site":28,
        "date":1461838525,
        "alt":1,
        "lng":2.1254144839295543,
        "lat":41.489062608088766,
        "type":"ble"
    }
]
}
```

7.1.1.2 Indoor Positioning Dashboard

A specific page has been deployed within Hit2Gap dashboard with the aim of visualizing incoming data from indoor positioning devices.

Figure 18. Dashboard layout for indoor positioning system

The layout is divided as follow:

Left side:

- 1) A map showing the last received coordinate, device position. Clicking on a place holder, a tooltip displays some information of the device and the corresponding line in the grid is selected.
- 2) A list of all registered nodes. This list is automatically refreshed to display all new nodes registered even if they do not send coordinates. Clicking on the list, the tooltip of the corresponding position is displayed on the map and the list of all registered positions for the selected node are displayed in the grid on the right side.

Right side:

- 1) A list displays all received coordinates for the device selected on the left side map or on the left side grid. This information can be filtered on a certain period of time.
- 2) A map where the position selected in the upper list is shown.

7.1.2 Example of data query for Challenger site

This is an example of JSON style configuration file used by the reading module to collect data from BMS database table. This structure can be easily adapted to collect data changing the SQL query structure

```
{
  "queryIfNoLastRead": "SELECT TOP (500) [Address] nodeid,[TimeStamp] timestamp,[Value] value
  FROM [TRANSFERT].[dbo].[VIZ_T_VIZELIA_COMPTEUR] (NOLOCK) WHERE
  [TimeStamp]>'2016-11-01' AND LogType=' ORDER BY [TimeStamp]",
  "query": "SELECT TOP (500) [Address] nodeid,[TimeStamp] timestamp,[Value] value FROM
  [TRANSFERT].[dbo].[VIZ_T_VIZELIA_COMPTEUR] (NOLOCK) WHERE [TimeStamp]>=? AND
  LogType=' ORDER BY [TimeStamp]",
  "connectionString": "jdbc:sqlserver://213.215.30.232:1433;user=.....;password=.....;",
  "pollingTimeInMs": 2000,
  "jdbcClassName": "com.microsoft.sqlserver.jdbc.SQLServerDriver",
  "lastReadTimestamp": true,
  "measureConfigurations":
  [
    {
      "phNodeIdentifier": "column.nodeid",
      "logNodeIdentifier": "0",
      "objIdHigh": "custom.highFromUom",
      "objIdLow": "custom.lowFromUom",
      "pk": "column.timestamp",
      "timestamp": "column.timestamp",
      "timestampFormat": "y-M-d H:m:s:S",
      "value": "custom.scaledValue"
    }
  ]
}
```

7.1.3 H2G MM-WSN

The usage of MM-WSN sensors is expected to achieve data collection currently not available without the need to integrate these sensors in the BMS operating on the site.

All the data produced by the MM-WSN include a common set of attributes (known as the metadata) following the format are shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Meta-Data produced by the MM-WSN.

Name	Unit	Data Type	Description
Node_id	N/A	UINT64	Identifier of the node producing the data
TimeStamp	seconds	UINT64	Timestamp represented in Unix timestamp (seconds since 00:00:00 UTC, 01/01/1970)
FeatureOfInterest	N/A	String	The feature that is being measured are taken (e.g. "room1", "front_window" or "area03")
Procedure	N/A	String	The sensor that produced the data (e.g. "sensor01", "datasensor", "temp_sensor")
ObservedProperty	N/A	String (enum)	The property that is measured: THL, PRESENCE, CONTACT or NWK_INFO

The ObservedProperty attribute specifies the actual data sent in the datastream:

- THL: temperature, humidity and light readings
- PRESENCE: presence readings.
- CONTACT: contact readings.
- NWK_INFO: network related information.

The measured data produced by the MM-WSN is shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Measured Data produced by the MM-WSN.

Name	Unit	Data Type	Description
Temperature	C°	INT16	The temperature measured by the device scaled by 100 (e.g. the value 2120 represents 21.2C°)
Humidity	%	UINT16	The relative humidity measured by the device scaled by 10 (e.g. the value 513 represents 51.3%)
Light	Lux	UINT16	The Light level measured by the device (e.g. the value 3250 represents 3250Lux)
Presence	N/A	BOOL	TRUE if a presence has been detected. FALSE otherwise.
Contact	N/A	BOOL	TRUE is the contact switch is closed. FALSE otherwise.

The device also produces information related to the network topology of the MM-WSN. This information is summarized in Table 9.

Table 9: Network Data of the MM-WSN.

Name	Unit	Data Type	Description
Parent_Id	N/A	UINT64	Identifier of the current parent of the node
Link_Quality	N/A	UINT8	The quality of the communication link between the node and its parent represented as a number in the range 0-255

The method used for collecting data from this sensor is described in the following sub-sections. The H2G MM-WSN device will connect to PLAT.ONE via an MQTT protocol communication using JSON format. The JSON payload has been designed to support only the exchange of Measurements types of information, i.e. from devices to platform only.

7.1.3.1 Message Topic

The MQTT client shall publish to an MQTT topic defined as follows: "JSON_MQTT"

7.1.3.2 Payload Fields

In general, the payload of the MQTT message appears as a JSON-formatted String, comprising a list of key-value pairs as in the example below:

```
{
```

```

    "field_id_1": "field_value_1",
    "field_id_1": "field_value_1",
    ...
    "field_id_N": "field_value_N"
}

```

The integration to MM-WSN is defined by the following JSON formats

- HIT2GAP-Tibucon.json

The admitted field types and the associated functionality are described in the introductory paragraph.

7.1.3.3 Payload Types

This payload is used to report messages from nodes to the platform. As soon as the platform receives such message, it creates a node instance using the “ID” value as node MAC address (the node type will be “Endpoint”).

All data token are as described in Table 7, 8 and 9 at the beginning of this section; Please note that the token labelled “start_time” represents the time stamp of the sent message.

Example:

```

{
  "node_id": "01234500345",
  "logical_node": [0],
  "FeatureOfInterest": "front_window",
  "Procedure": "temp_sensor",
  "ObservedProperty": "THL",
  "TEMPERATURE": 2510,
  "HUMIDITY": 500,
  "LIGHT": 6200,
  "start_time": "2016-07-06 10:34:27"
}

```

7.1.3.4 MM-WSN Dashboard

In this paragraph we describe the structure of the dashboard built for this type of network. As described in paragraph 7.1.3, these kinds of sensors are able to provide four different groups of measures. In order to manage this information in a flexible way the data collected by each node are divided into different logical nodes as described in the following images:

Figure 19. High level structure of a MM-WSN node

Each node is structured in four different logical nodes that will collect homogenous data, which are data belonging to the same topic.

Logical node 1 contains environmental data (temperature, humidity, luminosity) of a certain area;

Figure 20. Logical node 1 structure

Logical node 2 contains information on person's presence within the area:

Figure 21. Logical node 2 structure

Logical node 3 contains information on closed contact

Nodes-Node Configuration NSAP: 0.0.0.50 ID:4923		
Resources	Active	Enable
Physical Node		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Logical Node: 00:00:00:01		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Logical Node: 00:00:00:02		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Logical Node: 00:00:00:03		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
FeatureOfInterest		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Procedure		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
ObservedProperty		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Contact		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Figure 22. Logical node 3 structure

Logical node 4 belongs to network information.

Nodes-Node Configuration NSAP: 0.0.0.50 ID:4923		
Resources	Active	Enable
Physical Node		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Logical Node: 00:00:00:01		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Logical Node: 00:00:00:02		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Logical Node: 00:00:00:03		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Logical Node: 00:00:00:04		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Parent_ID		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Link Quality		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
FeatureOfInterest		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Procedure		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
ObservedProperty		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Figure 23. Logical node 4 structure

The data navigation in the dashboard will follow this structure and enable a data navigation coherent with it.

Figure 24. MM-WSN dashboard

The top left side navigation panel collects the list of available nodes, this list is automatically refreshed each time a node receives new data or a new node is added to the network.

List of Nodes	
Node ID	Last received
NSAP: 0.0.0.47	20/03/2017 10:05:39
NSAP: 0.0.0.48	20/03/2017 10:05:39
NSAP: 0.0.0.49	20/03/2017 10:05:39
NSAP: 0.0.0.50	20/03/2017 10:05:39
NSAP: 0.0.0.51	20/03/2017 10:05:39
NSAP: 0.0.0.52	20/03/2017 10:05:39
NSAP: 0.0.0.53	20/03/2017 10:05:39

Figure 25. MM-WSN nodes list

When a node is selected in the list the middle left panel is populated with the existing logical nodes reporting the value of the parameter “ObservedProperty”

Figure 26. MM-WSN logical nodes list

When the logical node is selected, the existing measures are presented in the lower left panel

Figure 27. MM-WSN measures belonging to a logical node

Selecting the requested measure, the two central panel displays into a grid, and if feasible, with a graph, the data belonging to a particular time frame (Hour, Day, Week, Month, Year or custom period).

Figure 28. MM-WSN measures value display

7.1.4 Build-Ax communication example

The example below downloads data between two dates into a file named oct10morning (use quotes for dates) from a BuildAx LRS with the Ip address 130.159.47.84.

```
./entget.bash -u user -p pass -ip 130.159.47.84 oct10morning -start '2015-10-07 00:00:01' -end '2015-10-07 07:20:00'
```

This command will copy to the platform existing encrypted files in the BuildAx LRS. Such files must be decrypted using an application provided by UOS (bax2csv), which must be embedded in the platform:

```
bax2csv fetch.bax data.csv
```

Files from BuildAx contain readings from multiple sensors. A typical result file for one sensor has the following aspect:

```
...
2015/03/03,14:25:03,42E3ED59,-67,1,200,20,3063,45.05,162,0,0,24032,1
2015/03/03,14:27:41,42144AC2,-104,1,82,20,3079,39.66,173,111,0,12806,1
2015/03/03,14:29:19,42555078,-59,1,50,20,3072,35.26,176,5,0,40698,1
2015/03/03,14:30:22,42E3ED59,-68,1,201,20,3064,45.09,162,0,0,28182,1
2015/03/03,14:34:44,42555078,-59,1,51,20,3072,35.26,176,3,0,48183,1
2015/03/03,14:35:40,42E3ED59,-66,1,202,20,3064,45.03,162,0,0,32349,1
...
```

where:

```
2015/03/03 is the date
14:25:03 is the time (hh:mm:ss)
42E3ED59 is the 8 character ID of the BuildAX ENV sensor
-67 is the radio signal strength
1 is the packet type: 1=normal, 2=PIR event, 3=Switch event
200 packet counter
20 can be ignored
3063 is the battery level mV
45.05 is the humidity
162 it temperature in tenths of a degree i.e. 16.2C
0 lux level
0 PIR event counter
24032 PIR energy level (needs to be post-processed)
1 Switch event counter (increments as events are recorded)
```

7.1.5 PLAT.ONE MODBUS/IP protocol parameters

In this section we briefly describe an example of configuration of MODBUS/IP to be used by PLAT.ONE for establishing the necessary communication

Table 10: PLAT.ONE MODBUS/IP parameter specification.

<code>"devices":</code>	
<code>[{</code>	
<code>"ip": "172.30.31.105",</code>	<i>IP Address of the device</i>
<code>"port": 502,</code>	<i>Accessible port for the addressed device</i>
<code>"unitid": 105,</code>	<i>Id of the addressed unit</i>
<code>"regoffset": 0,</code>	
<code>"measures": [</code>	
<code>{</code>	
<code>"polling": 30000</code>	<i>Wait time (in milliseconds) between consecutive Modbus operations on the same register</i>
<code>"regaddr": 0</code>	<i>Starting register for the Modbus operation</i>
<code>"regcount": 2</code>	<i>Number of register addressed by the Modbus operation</i>
<code>"functionmod":</code>	<i>Modbus function code of the operation to be performed on the set of registers specified by regaddr, regcount</i>
<code>"writeFunctionCode": 4</code>	<i>The Modbus function code to be used for writing onto the register set. If > 0, a write command will be associated to the registers</i>
<code>"commandObjidh": 1</code>	<i>Use this value and commandObjidl to add a write command (having a certain objectId high, low) to the node that will be created to represent this Modbus server. Used only when writeFunctionCode is specified and > 0</i>
<code>"commandObjidl": 1</code>	<i>Use this value and commandObjidh to add a write command (having a certain objectId high, low) to the node that will be created to represent this Modbus server. Used only when writeFunctionCode is specified and > 0</i>
<code>"reverseByte": false</code>	<i>Set to true to swap the bit order in a certain byte. Normally set to false</i>
<code>"waitBeforeTrans": true</code>	<i>If set to true, a certain wait time will be observed before each reading operation to the server. This interval is set to 2 seconds by default; it may be changed by setting the Dory custom property "waitBeforeTransaction" (e.g. waitBeforeTransaction=500 will set a 500 msec wait time)</i>
<code>"reconnectBeforeTrans": false</code>	<i>Parameter for the Modbus transaction. Forces an automatic reconnection before each transaction. Normally set to false</i>
<code>},</code>	
<code>]</code>	